

A STUDY ON ADOPTABILITY OF JUTE FIBRE FOR REINFORCING CEMENT MORTAR

LAKSHMI H S

Research Scholar, Department of Civil Engineering, M S Ramaiah Institute of Technology, Bengaluru.

Dr. ANILKUMAR R

Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, M S Ramaiah Institute of Technology, Bengaluru.

Abstract

Natural fibres offer numerous benefits for the environment and construction practices. They are eco-friendly, cost-effective, lightweight, renewable, and exhibit superior thermal and corrosion resistance. Using natural fibres enhances mechanical properties and supports sustainable building methods, making them an excellent choice for promoting green construction. The strength of cement mortar can be effectively increased by using natural jute fibre will not only consider approaches to improve the properties of cement mortar; This will examine more than just how to improve cement mortar's properties, but it will also investigate using jute and limiting the use of artificial fibres, which are bad for the environment. It was determined to conduct an experimental study on the compressive strength of cement mortar reinforced with jute fibres in order to achieve this. As reinforcement, fibres of varying lengths that were uniformly distributed throughout the matrix and randomly orientated were used. In direct compression, samples with variable fibre contents (volume fractions) were determined. The introduction of jute fibre into standard-sized cubes has been done while experimenting with the proportions of the materials in the cement mortar, the water-cement ratio, and the aspect ratio of the fibre mentioned fibre mentioned. Prepared samples are were subjected to compression strength test using the appropriate testing apparatus in compliance with approved guidelines. The outcomes of JFRCM were contrasted with those of the standard cement mortar. According to the investigation's findings, adding jute fibres can improve When utilised in shorter lengths and lower volume contents, cement mortar retains its strength properties; however, jute fibres with a larger volume content cause cement mortar to start losing these properties. The findings indicate the potential of utilizing jute fibres to create affordable construction materials, especially for applications such as roofing, wall panels, and building boards, particularly in regions where jute fibres are abundant.

Keywords: Jute Fibres, Aspect Ratio, Cement Mortar, Composites, Sustainable.

INTRODUCTION

Fibre Reinforced Concrete (FRC) is a composite material that incorporates fibrous elements to enhance its structural performance. This material is a combination of cement, mortar, or concrete reinforced with discrete, evenly distributed fibres. These fibres are typically added to concrete to strengthen and prolong its strength by decreasing cracks brought on by plastic shrinkage and drying. While the fibres are being used in concrete for the above said advantages, the same can be utilised in cement mortar to derive similar benefits.

Jute Fibre

Jute fibre, derived from the outer layers of jute plants, is among the most robust, affordable, and long-lasting natural fibres. It is entirely biodegradable, recyclable, and environmentally sustainable.

The high cellulose content in jute fibres contributes significantly to their remarkable strength. Moreover, jute stands out as the most cost-effective, versatile, and widely available natural fibre compared to others.

Objectives

1. To Assess the impact of incorporating jute fibres in cement mortar.
2. To Identify the optimal percentage of jute fibres to be added to a 1:3 cement mortar mix, using four variations: 0.5%, 1%, 1.5%, and 2%.
3. To Evaluate the compressive strength of fibre-reinforced cement mortar (1:3) and compare it to that of conventional cement mortar.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Researchers have focused towards carrying out their investigations to study the engineering properties of fibre reinforced mortar productions to arrest cracks. Among all these research works only few focuses on jute fibre and its utilization the literature survey on utilization of jute fibres are as follows

Pereira et al. (2015) explored the mechanical behavior of cement mortar reinforced with sisal fibres. Their findings highlighted the superior performance of the reinforced material compared to plain cement mortar, particularly when long fibres were utilized, as supported by impact test results.

The impact of several treatments on the chemical and structural characteristics of fibres obtained from two xerophytic plants, Doum (*Chamaerops humilis*) and Diss (*Ampelodesmos mauritanicus*), was examined by Achour et al. (2017). The study's primary objective was to reinforce a connection between these fibres and the cement matrix. It also examined the effects of different fibre inclusion rates on the mechanical, thermal, and physical characteristics of cement composites. It was shown that treating Doum and Diss fibres with 1% and 3% NaOH improved their properties using various approaches such as scanning electron microscopy, X-ray diffraction, and infrared spectroscopy. These fibre-reinforced mortars showed improved water absorption, greater porosity, and decreased bulk density and compressive strength. Importantly, composites reinforced with 2% treated Diss fibres and 1.5% treated Doum fibres demonstrated better flexural strength. Mortars reinforced with these fibres showed improved water absorption, greater porosity, and decreased bulk density and compressive strength. It is noteworthy that composites reinforced with 1.5% treated Doum fibres and 2% treated Diss fibres showed improved flexural strength. Additionally, studies of thermal conductivity at various drying stages showed how water content affects thermal characteristics. According to thermogravimetric analysis and differential scanning calorimetry, adding these fibres improves the composites' heat absorption and tolerance to high temperatures while lowering thermal conductivity. Codispoti et al. (2015) conducted a detailed experimental study to assess the mechanical properties of natural fibres for their potential use in strengthening masonry structures.

The physical and mechanical properties of flax, hemp, jute, sisal, and coir fibres were assessed in this study. To create composite materials, the fibres that performed the best were subsequently evaluated with three distinct matrices, including two that were based on organic components. The findings from these experiments offer a valuable resource for understanding the capabilities of natural fibres as effective reinforcement materials.

Yaseen et al. (2013) discussed the renewable and sustainable nature of natural fibres, noting that their use in construction materials dates back centuries. Historically, horsehair was mixed with mortar, and straw was used in mud bricks, while plant-based materials such as bamboo, jute, akwara, elephant grass, sisal, and coir have also been utilized. Their research explored the incorporation of human hair fibres (HHF) as reinforcement in cement-based materials. Fibres of consistent diameter and varying lengths, with aspect ratios between 500 and 700 and fibre content ranging from 0% to 1% by volume, were tested. The study observed at how fibre content affected mechanical properties and load-deflection behavior at two water-to-cement (w/c) ratios (0.6 and 0.7). Results indicated improved energy absorption capacity with fibre inclusion, with an optimal fibre volume fraction of 0.8%. These findings highlight the potential for further exploration of this cost-effective reinforcement method in structural applications, particularly in high-strength cementitious materials.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Procedure: Materials

The raw, locally accessible jute fiber depicted in Figure 1 was utilized untreated. With a cut length of around 1 cm, as established by the aspect ratio (l/d) = 60, and a diameter "d" of 0.016 cm, this jute fiber was added to the cement mortar mixture in four different volumetric percentages: 0.5%, 1%, 1.5%, and 2%. The binding material used was regular Portland cement, which typically had a consistency of 27%. Sand was utilized as a fine aggregate that was retained on a 90-micron sieve after passing through 2 mm.

Fig 1: Jute Fibre

Cement Mortar Mix

Mix design refers to the method of choosing appropriate ingredients and determining their proportions to create a cement mortar mix. This process ensures that the necessary amounts of cement and fine aggregate are available and establishes a relationship between the water/cement ratio and the target strength. In this study, a cement-to-sand mix ratio of 1:3 was carefully maintained. Initially, a conventional unreinforced plain cement mortar mix was prepared. Subsequently, jute fibres cut to a length of 1 cm were incorporated into another cement mortar mix in varying volumetric contents of 0.5%, 1%, 1.5%, and 2%. The mixing process was closely observed to achieve an optimal distribution of the jute fibres. Finally, samples were prepared for further evaluation.

Preparation of the Test Specimen

The weight of cement and sand was batched according to the mix design (1200 g: 3600 g). The sand particles were sieved which was passing through 2 mm and retained on 90 microns was taken for the test. Initially the two dry ingredients were mixed together and kept aside. For the dry mix, the different fibre contents 0.5%, 1%, 1.5%, 2% were used. The weight of jute fibres was cut and taken by the weight of cement, for example, for 0.5% - 6 g (i.e., $1200 \times 0.5\%$). A total of 54 cubes of size 70.6 mm \times 70.6 mm \times 70.6 mm was cast to determine the compressive of the composites, respectively. The fibres were prepared by cut into a length of 1 cm manually. The ingredients were manually mixed, ensuring that jute fibres were gradually and evenly incorporated into the cement mortar to achieve a uniform distribution throughout the mixture. Water was then incorporated to the mix, and the process continued until a consistent texture was obtained. The mixing process lasted approximately 3 minutes. Once prepared, the freshly mixed mortar was poured into cube-shaped moulds. The specimens were kept in the moulds for 24 hours before being demoulded and eventually cured in water for periods of 7 and 28 days. After the curing phase, the specimens were air-dried prior to testing.

Fig 2: Casting of cubes

Fig 3: Cubes kept for curing

Experimental Program

The impetus of this research is to analyze the compressive strength of cement mortar composites reinforced with jute fibre to that of regular cement mortar. A Compression Testing Machine was used to perform the compressive strength testing.

Compressive Strength Testing

The compressive strength of cement mortar refers to its capacity to withstand a static load that aims to crush it. Conducting compressive strength tests provides a clear understanding of how the strength varies with an increase in fibre volume dosage in the test specimens.

Fig 4: Cubes after compression test

Fig 5: Cubes after compression test

Fig 6: Cubes after compression test

RESULTS

The performance of fibre-cement composites, primarily influenced by the interaction between the fibres and the surrounding cement matrix, is determined by several factors. These include the physical properties of the fibres, as well as the chemical composition of the fibres. Experiments were conducted to assess the impact of jute fibres, with the findings illustrated in graphical form. (Figs. 1,2,3,4 and 5).

Table 1: Compressive Strength results of different percentages of fibre content

Cube No.			Compressive Strength – 7Days (MPa)	Cube No.			Compressive Strength – 28 Days (MPa)	Fibre Content (%)
1	2	3		1	2	3		
21.2	20.9	19.8	20.63	23.7	24.1	25.9	24.5	Plain Cement Mortar
23.6	22.4	24.8	23.61	28.4	28.5	28.2	28.36	0.5%
28.9	28.2	28.7	28.6	30.9	32.9	31.1	31.63	1%
29.7	28.5	30.9	29.7	36.3	34.4	38.4	36.36	1.5%
28.8	26.5	31.1	26.3	22.2	24.3	20.96	29.46	2%

Fig 7: Graphical representation of compressive strength observed at 7 days and 28 days for 0.5% fibre content

Fig 8: Graphical representation of compressive strength observed at 7 days and 28 days for 0.5% fibre content

Fig 9: Graphical representation of compressive strength observed at 7 days and 28 days for 1% fibre content

Fig 10: Graphical representation of compressive strength observed at 7 days and 28 days for 1.5% fibre content

Compressive Strength result for cube after 7 days and 28 days curing

Fig 11: graphical representation of comparison of compressive strength of different fibre contents

DISCUSSIONS

The experimental results data brought the following discussions:

- 1 The percentage difference in compressive strength between Jute Fibre Reinforced Cement Mortar (JFRCM) and regular cement mortar is shown in Figure 11 for each of the four jute fibre content dosages in mix ratios of 1:3.
- 2 When plain cement mortar is made without any jute, it can be said that all fibre contents exhibit a remarkable enrichment of compressive strength over the course of the 7- and 28-day curing periods. However, the cement mortar's compressive strength decreases for the 28-day curing period when the fibre content is 2%.
- 3 When compared to plain cement mortar, administered in 1: 3 mix ratios, a 50% increase in compressive strength is seen at 7 and 28 days of curing for 1.5% fiber content. The maximum compressive strength is 36 MPa for 28 days, which is regarded as the ideal outcome.

CONCLUSIONS

1. This project focused on studying the behavior of natural fibres of uniform length specifically jute in cement mortars.
2. Fibre-reinforced mortar specimens demonstrated greater stability under load compared to plain, unreinforced mortar specimens. Utilizing jute fibre in cement mortar presents a promising opportunity for sustainable development in India, where jute is cultivated abundantly.
3. The experimental investigations revealed that incorporating jute fibres significantly improved the compressive strength of cement mortar when specific fibre lengths and volume contents were used. In particular, the compressive strength was maximized at a fibre content of 1.5% and a fibre length of 10 mm. Conversely, an increase in fibre content beyond this threshold adversely impacted compressive strength. The highest recorded improvement in compressive strength was 36.36% compared to plain cement mortar. This indicates that Jute Fibre Reinforced Cement Mortar (JFRCM) can be efficiently developed using locally sourced jute. The affordability, renewability, lightweight nature, and environmental benefits of jute further underscore the socioeconomic feasibility of JFRCM. Based on the findings, incorporating jute fibre into fibre-reinforced mortar composites emerges as a promising approach to enhancing the performance of cement mortars.
4. To summarize, the results indicate an appreciable improvement in the compressive strength of reinforced mortar compared to plain cement mortar.
5. Even after crack formation and fractures, the samples maintained their structural stability. Jute fibres offer a sustainable and eco-friendly construction material with noteworthy mechanical properties.

Future Scope of the Study

Material can be used for environmentally friendly construction techniques and If FRM is going to pass test for durability and chemical attack we can go with ready mix (dry) of FRM.

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